

Quantum Brownian motion and generalization of Arrhenius rate law[†]

Bidhan Chandra Bag^a, Dhruva Banerjee^b, Suman Kumar Banik^c and Deb Shankar Ray^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Shantiniketan-731 235, India

^bIndian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : pcdrs@mahendra.iacs.res.in Fax : 91-33-24722805

^cMax-Planck-Institut für Physik Komplexer Systeme, Nothnitzer Strabe 38, 01187 Dresden, Germany

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Arrhenius rate law is now more than hundred years old. The dynamical basis of this phenomenological law was provided by Kramers in early nineteenforties. Since late seventies, the extensive experimental investigation in chemical dynamics and allied areas centered around Kramers' dynamical rate theory. The present paper is an outline of further development of rate theory in quantum mechanical context which takes into account of thermal activation and tunneling within an unified description. The theory is based on a new scheme for quantum Brownian motion recently proposed by us to establish quantum analogues of Kramers', Smoluchowski and Fokker-Planck equations with true probability distribution functions in *c*-number phase space.

Introduction

The true universality of rate constant of a chemical reaction lies in the phenomenological law of Arrhenius,

$$k = A \exp\left[-\frac{E}{k_B T}\right]$$

proposed more than hundred years ago. Here *E* denotes the activation energy for the reaction carried out at a temperature *T* and *k_B* is the Boltzmann constant. *A* is a preexponential factor which depends on various thermodynamic and dynamical factors and forms the essential content of rate theory. The theoretical basis of the Arrhenius rate law rests on equilibrium statistical mechanics and more generally on non-equilibrium stochastic processes^{1,2}. It is our purpose, in this paper, to review some of the recent developments in the latter area in connection with the quantum dynamical generalization of the reaction law in condensed media.

A first step towards understanding the rate coefficient is thermodynamics of equilibrium statistical mechanics. Consider a simple reaction in one dimension proceeding along a reaction coordinate *x* where the potential energy is given by *V(x)* as shown in Fig. 1. *x* = 0 and *x* = *x_b* correspond to the reactant and the transition states, respectively. Thermalization of the reactant in the left can well be described by a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution *P(x, v)* =

$$z \exp\left[-\frac{\frac{1}{2}v^2 + V(x)}{k_B T}\right], \text{ where } v \text{ is the velocity of the particle,}$$

Fig. 1. A schematic representation of potential energy $V(x) = -\frac{1}{3}Ax^3 + Bx^2$.

z the normalization constant. Linearizing the potential *V(x)* at *x* = 0, such that $V(x) = V(0) + \frac{1}{2}\omega_0^2 x^2$, where $\omega_0^2 = V''(x)|_{x=0}$, one may determine, *z* by the normalization

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(x, v) dx dv = 1 \text{ as } z = \frac{w_0}{2\pi k_B T} \exp\left[\frac{V(0)}{k_B T}\right].$$

If we now assume that the same equilibrium distribution prevails at *x* = *x_b* so that at this point $P(x_b, v) =$

$$z \exp\left[-\frac{\frac{1}{2}v^2 + V(x_b)}{k_B T}\right] \text{ then the rate constant can be}$$

calculated as $k = \int_0^{\infty} v P(x_b, v) dv$, which represents the average positive velocity of the particle at the barrier top. This yields the celebrated result of transition state theory;

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

$$k = \frac{w_0}{2\pi} \exp \left[- \frac{E}{k_B T} \right], \text{ where } V(x_b) - V(0) = E \text{ and } \frac{w_0}{2\pi} \text{ is}$$

the frequency of oscillation of the particle in the left well. According to transition state theory, the preexponential factor A in Arrhenius rate law can thus be interpreted as the bounce frequency in the reactant well.

The ansatz of an equilibrium distribution at the barrier top is an assumption which is not, in general, true. The simple reason is that a large difference in concentration at $x = 0$ and $x = x_b$ (once the concentration of the reactant is kept large deep in the well and very low at the barrier top) sets up a concentration gradient along the reaction coordinate resulting in a diffusion current at $x = x_b$. This implies that a strong nonequilibrium situation prevails at the barrier top. It is therefore necessary to take into consideration of this nonequilibrium condition in terms of a non-equilibrium distribution which describes the steady diffusion current within the framework of a rate theory. Kramers¹ addressed this problem in 1940 by generalizing Einstein's theory of Brownian motion in phase space (x, v) to develop what is known as Kramers' equation for non-equilibrium phase space distribution function. By virtue of Brownian motion the motion of the reaction coordinate is not only guided by the potential but also by the surrounding medium of viscosity γ in which the reaction is carried out. Kramers worked out in detail the two limiting expressions for the rate constant,

$$k = \frac{\omega_0}{2\pi} \left\{ \frac{-\gamma + \sqrt{(\gamma/2)^2 + w_b^2}}{\omega_b} \right\} e^{-\frac{E}{k_B T}}$$

and $k = \gamma \frac{E}{k_B T} e^{-\frac{E}{k_B T}}$, in the intermediate of strong and low

viscosity regimes¹, respectively. Here ω_b represents the linearized frequency of the inverted well at $x = x_b$. It is important to note that although the form of Arrhenius rate coefficient k is universal its dependence on transport coefficient like viscosity is dramatically different as one passes from high viscosity to low viscosity regime.

With the advent of pulsed lasers, eighties show a tremendous growth of experimental chemical dynamics around this theoretical development, which was extended to include further the memory effects and other related aspects²⁻¹³. An important endeavour in this direction is the generalization of the theory to quantum domain. Based on a coherent state representation of quantum noise and a new scheme of ensemble averaging procedure we have very recently developed a quantum theory of Brownian motion

in phase space¹⁴⁻¹⁶. An important off-shoot is the quantum Kramers' equation¹⁵ which is valid for arbitrary temperature and friction. The theory is equipped to deal with thermal activation and tunneling on an equal footing. In the present paper we give a brief outline of this development taking into consideration of the high and low friction limits to derive the corresponding rate expressions in an appropriate way. We point out in passing that the theory is independent of path integral approach, which has been traditionally used as a description of quantum Brownian motion since eighties.

Quantum Brownian motion and Langevin equation in C-numbers

The Hamiltonian¹⁷ of a particle moving in an external potential field and coupled to its environmental represented by a set of harmonic oscillators with frequencies $\{\omega_j\}$ is given by

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hat{P}^2}{2} + V(\hat{X}) + \sum_j \left[\frac{\hat{P}_j^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} k_j (\hat{q}_j - \hat{X})^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

Here \hat{X} and \hat{P} are coordinate and momentum operators of the particle and the set $\{\hat{q}_j, \hat{p}_j\}$ is the set of coordinate and momentum operators for the reservoir oscillators coupled linearly to the system through their coupling coefficients k_j . The potential $V(\hat{X})$ is due to the external force field for the Brownian particle. The coordinate and momentum operators follow the usual commutation relation $[\hat{X}, \hat{P}] = i\hbar$ and $[\hat{q}_j, \hat{p}_j] = i\hbar \delta_{ij}$.

We eliminate the reservoir degrees of freedom in the usual way^{18,19} to obtain the operator Langevin equation for the particle.

$$\ddot{\hat{X}}(t) + \int_0^t dt' \beta(t-t') \dot{\hat{X}}(t') + V'(\hat{X}) = \hat{F}(t) \quad (2)$$

where the noise operator $\hat{F}(t)$ and the memory kernel $\beta(t)$ are given by

$$\hat{F}(t) = \sum_j [\{\hat{q}_j(0) - \hat{X}(0)\} k_j \cos \omega_j t + \hat{p}_j(0) k_j^{1/2} \sin \omega_j t] \quad (3)$$

and

$$\beta(t) = \sum_j k_j \cos \omega_j t \quad (4)$$

with $k_j = w_j^2$ (masses have been assumed to be unity).

Eq. (2) is an exact quantized operator Langevin equation for which the noise properties of $\hat{F}(t)$ can be defined using a suitable initial canonical distribution of the bath coordinates

and momenta. Our aim here is to replace it by an equivalent quantum generalized Langevin equation (QGLE) in c -numbers. We achieve this in two steps. We *first* carry out the *quantum mechanical average* of eq. (2),

$$\langle \ddot{\hat{X}}(t) \rangle + \int_0^t dt' \beta(t-t') \langle \dot{\hat{X}}(t') \rangle + \langle V'(\hat{X}) \rangle = \hat{F}(t) \quad (5)$$

where the average $\langle \dots \rangle$ is taken over the initial product separable quantum states of the particle and the bath oscillators at $t = 0$, $|\phi\rangle\{|\alpha_1\rangle|\alpha_2\rangle \dots |\alpha_N\rangle\}$. Here $|\phi\rangle$ denotes any arbitrary initial state of the particle and $|\alpha_i\rangle$ corresponds to the initial coherent state of the i -th bath oscillator. $|\alpha_i\rangle$ is given by $|\alpha_i\rangle = \exp(-|\alpha_i|^2/2) \sum_{n_i=0}^{\infty} (\alpha_i^{n_i} / \sqrt{n_i!}) |n_i\rangle$, α_i being expressed in terms of the mean values of the coordinate and momentum of the i -th oscillator, $\langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle = (\sqrt{\hbar}/2\omega_j) (\alpha_j + \alpha_j^\dagger)$ and $\langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle = i\sqrt{\hbar\omega_j}/2 (\alpha_j^\dagger - \alpha_j)$, respectively. It is important to note that $\langle \hat{F}(t) \rangle$ of eq. (5) is a classical-like noise term which, in general, is a non-zero number because of the quantum mechanical averaging and is given by

$$\hat{F}(t) = \sum_j \{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \} k_j \cos \omega_j t + \langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle k_j^{1/2} \sin \omega_j t \quad (6)$$

it is convenient to rewrite the c -number eqn. (5) as

$$\langle \ddot{\hat{X}}(t) \rangle + \int_0^t dt' \beta(t-t') \langle \dot{\hat{X}}(t') \rangle + \langle V'(\hat{X}) \rangle = \hat{F}(t) \quad (7)$$

where we let the quantum mechanical mean value $\langle \hat{F}(t) \rangle = F(t)$. In the next step we turn to the *second* average. To realize $F(t)$ as an effective c -number noise we now assume that the momenta $\langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle$ and the shifted coordinates $\{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \}$ of the bath oscillators are distributed according to a canonical distribution of Gaussian forms as

$$P_j = N \exp \left\{ \frac{-[\langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle^2 + k_j \{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \}^2]}{2\hbar\omega_j \left(\bar{n}_j + \frac{1}{2} \right)} \right\} \quad (8)$$

so that for any quantum mechanical mean value $O_j(\langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle, \{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \})$ the statistical average $\langle \dots \rangle_s$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_j \rangle_s &= \int O_j(\langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle, \{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \}) \\ &\times P_j(\langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle, \{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \}) \\ &\times d \langle \hat{p}_j(0) \rangle d \{ \langle \hat{q}_j(0) \rangle - \langle \hat{X}(0) \rangle \} \end{aligned}$$

Here \bar{n}_j indicates the average thermal photon number of the j -th oscillator at temp. T and $\bar{n}_j = 1/[\exp(\hbar\omega_j/k_B T) - 1]$ and

N is the normalization constant.

The distribution (8) and the definition of statistical average (9) imply that $F(t)$ must satisfy

$$\langle F(t) \rangle_s = 0 \quad (10)$$

and

$$\langle F(t)F(t') \rangle_s = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j k_j \hbar \omega_j \left(\cot h \frac{\hbar \omega_j}{2k_B T} \right) \cos \omega_j (t-t') \quad (11)$$

That is, the c -number noise $F(t)$ is such that it is zero-centered and satisfies the standard quantum fluctuation-dissipation relation (FDR) as known in the literature^{18,19} in terms of quantum statistical average of the noise operators. The distribution (8) is thus an ansatz introduced to calculate the ensemble average over the quantum-mechanical mean values of noise properties of the bath, i.e. the quantum fluctuation-dissipation relation for the c -number quantum noise (11) along with (10). Secondly, the distribution (8) has a form which is Boltzman-like (but not a Boltzmann distribution) since the width parameter of the Boltzmann distribution kT gets replaced by $\hbar\omega_j(\bar{n}_j + \frac{1}{2})$. The vacuum term $\frac{1}{2}$ prevents the distribution function from being singular at $T = 0$.

To proceed further we now add the force term $V'(\langle \hat{x} \rangle)$ on both sides of eq. (7) and rearrange it to obtain formally

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \int_0^t dt' \beta(t-t') \dot{x}(t') + V'(x) = F(t) + Q(x, t) \quad (12)$$

where we let $\langle \hat{X}(t) \rangle = x(t)$ for simple notational convenience and

$$Q(x, t) = V'(x) - \langle V'(\hat{X}) \rangle \quad (13)$$

represents a quantum fluctuation term which offers a simple interpretation. This implies that the classical looking QGLE is governed by a c -number quantum noise $F(t)$ which originates from the quantum mechanical heat bath characterized by the properties (10) and (11) and a quantum fluctuation term $Q(x, t)$ due to the quantum nature of the system characteristic of the nonlinearity of the potential. The procedure has been recently implemented by us to formulate a quantum theory of Brownian motion¹⁴ and to propose an *exact* non-Markovian quantum Kramers' equation¹⁵ in phase space (x, \dot{x}) with *true probability distribution functions*.

Now we note that the generalized quantum Langevin equation (12) of a Brownian particle in presence of an external force field takes case of arbitrary coupling between the system and heat bath and contains quantum corrections, $Q(x, t)$ due to system to all orders. To make the later assertion

explicit we now express the operators \hat{X} and \hat{P} as

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{X}(t) &= \langle \hat{X}(t) \rangle + \delta \hat{X}(t) \\ \hat{P}(t) &= \langle \hat{P}(t) \rangle + \delta \hat{P}(t)\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

By construction $\langle \delta \hat{X}(t) \rangle = 0, \langle \delta \hat{P}(t) \rangle = 0$ and $[\delta \hat{X}, \delta \hat{P}] = i\hbar$. Expanding $\langle V(\hat{X}) \rangle$ around $\langle \hat{X} \rangle (\equiv x)$ in a Taylor series we obtain,

$$\langle V(\hat{X}) \rangle = V(x) + \frac{1}{2} V''(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^2 \rangle + \dots \quad (15)$$

Therefore $Q(t)$ can be expressed as

$$Q(t) = - \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} V^n(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(t) \rangle \quad (16)$$

Here $V^n(x)$ denotes the n -th derivative of the classical potential. The role of $Q(x, t)$ is therefore to modify the classical potential $V(x)$ in eq. (12). $Q(x, t)$ can be calculated by solving $\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle$ order by order. To the lowest order (second) $\langle \hat{X} \rangle$ and $\langle \delta \hat{X}^2 \rangle$ follow a coupled set of equations as given in Ref. 14. For higher order equations, e.g. the fourth order equations, we refer to Ref. 20.

Large friction limit; quantum Smoluchowski equation and decay of a metastable state

We now consider the diffusion of a particle in an external potential $V(x)$ as described by eq. (12). In the overdamped limit we drop the inertial term \ddot{x} and assume a Lorentzian density of modes of heat bath oscillators of the form $\kappa(\omega)\rho(\omega) = (2/\pi)[\gamma/(1+\omega^2\tau_c^2)]$, which in the limit $\tau_c \rightarrow 0$ results in a damping kernel $\beta(t-t') = \gamma\delta(t-t')$. Eq. (12) then assumes the form,

$$\dot{x} + \frac{1}{\gamma} V'_{\text{quant}}(x, t) = \frac{F(t)}{\gamma} \quad (17)$$

where we have expressed the effective quantum potential $V_{\text{quant}}(x, t)$ as $V'_{\text{quant}}(x, t) = V'(x) - Q(x, t)$. The equivalent description of eq. (17) in terms of true probability distribution $p(x, t)$ is given by

$$\frac{\partial p(x, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [V'_{\text{quant}} p(x, t)] + D_{\text{qo}} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \quad (18)$$

Here D_{qo} is the general expression for quantum diffusion coefficient in the overdamped limit and is given by

$$D_{\text{qo}} = \frac{2}{\gamma} \frac{1}{\pi \Delta t} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{1+\omega^2\tau_c^2} \hbar\omega [2\bar{n}(\omega) + 1] \times \frac{1}{\omega^2} \sin^2 \frac{\omega \Delta t}{2} d\omega, \tau_c \rightarrow 0 \quad (19)$$

where we have put the Lorentzian density of states for bath oscillator as stated earlier. $\bar{n}(\omega)$ is the average thermal photon number of the bath and is given by $\bar{n}(\omega) = 1/[\exp(\hbar\omega/k_B T) - 1]$. The quantum diffusion coefficient can thus be calculated exactly by numerical integration over the bath frequencies ω for $\tau_c \rightarrow 0$ (the Markovian limit). The following two limiting situations are further relevant for the present case : (i) in the high temperature limit $k_B T \gg \hbar\omega$, the quantity $\hbar\omega [2\bar{n}(\omega) + 1]$ in eq. (19) reduces to $k_B T$ and the explicit integration results in $D_{\text{qo}} = k_B T/\gamma$, the usual Einstein's value in the static friction limit. (ii) In the vacuum limit of the other hand $\bar{n} \rightarrow 0$ and D_{qo} may be obtained by considering the fact that the frequency dependence of the

integration in (19) except $\frac{1}{\omega^2} \sin^2 \frac{\omega \Delta t}{2}$ is flat (Markovian).

This results in $D_{\text{qo}} \approx \hbar\tilde{\omega}/2\gamma$, where $\tilde{\omega}$ is an average bath frequency which may be approximately taken to be the linearized frequency of oscillation in the well ω_0 (i.e., $\tilde{\omega} \sim \omega_0$) since at $T \sim 0$ the dynamics is dominated by population at the bottom of the well. For an arbitrary intermediate temperature we must rely, however, on the general expression (19) for the quantum diffusion coefficient.

To complete the description of quantum Smoluchowski equation (18) it is necessary to calculate the corrections $\langle \delta \hat{X}^2(t) \rangle, \langle \delta \hat{X}^3(t) \rangle$, etc. To this end we first return to operator eq. (2) and make use of the relation (14) and a Taylor expansion of the potential $V(\hat{X})$ to derive the following coupled equations in the overdamped limit :

$$\gamma \dot{x} + V'(x) + \sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{1}{n!} V_{n+1}(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle = F(t) \quad (20)$$

$$\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle = -\frac{n}{\gamma} V''(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle \quad (21)$$

where $n = 2, 3, \dots$. A decisive advantage in the treatment of overdamped limit is noteworthy. The equations for quantum corrections $\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle, n = 2, 3, \dots$ are closed in contrast to quantum mechanics of the system with nonlinear potential decoupled from the surrounding. If one is interested in the local dynamics around a point x_0 (say, at the bottom or top of a potential well) the set of eq. (21) gets decoupled from (20) to provide simple estimates of $\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle$ for $n = 2, 3, \dots$ since $V''(x_0)$ can be treated as a constant in such cases. Eq. (18) can be combined to eq. (21) to provide an extended phase space description in terms of a true probability function $p(x, \eta_2, \eta_3, \dots, t)$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \phi(x, \eta_2, \eta_3, \dots, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \sum_{n \geq 2} n V''(x) \eta_n p \\ &+ \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [V(x)p] + \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{1}{n!} V_{n+1}(x)p \right] \\ &+ D_{q_0} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where η_n ($\equiv \langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle$) for $n = 2, 3, \dots$ span the space of variables signifying quantum corrections around quantum mechanical mean position x .

We now discuss the classical and vacuum limits of quantum Smoluchowski equation (18). As mentioned earlier in the classical limit, D_{q_0} reduces to Einstein's classical diffusion coefficient $k_B T / \gamma$. At the same time $Q(x, t)$ vanishes so that $V_{\text{quant}}(x, t)$ goes over to $V(x)$ and one recovers the usual classical Smoluchowski equation. In the opposite limit as $T \rightarrow 0$, however, both quantum noise due to system and vacuum fluctuation originating from the heat bath make significant contribution. D_{q_0} in this limit assumes the form $\hbar \omega_0 / 2\gamma$. Another noteworthy feature of quantum Smoluchowski(18)[or (22)] is that unlike Wigner function based equations it does not contain higher (than two) order derivatives of probability distribution function. The positive definiteness of this function is therefore ensured. We are now in a position to consider the problem of escape from a metastable state. Over the last two decades this has attracted a lot of attention in classical theory of thermally activated processes. Since a quantum analysis naturally includes tunneling as an integral part of the problem we turn to this issue in search of an unified description of tunneling and thermal activation.

We first take into consideration of the time-scale of free motion of the system, $\omega(\omega^2 = V'')$. Since according to eq. (21) quantum correction $\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle$ varies on a time-scale $(n\omega^2/\gamma)^{-1}$ it is convenient to make an average of this fluctuation over a period and replace $\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle$ by an average $\overline{\langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle} = \omega \int_0^{1/\omega} \langle \delta \hat{X}^n(t) \rangle dt$. This implies that quantum noise does not change significantly on a time-scale during which the system relaxes so that $\tilde{V}(x)$ does not depend on time explicitly. Eq. (18) can then be recast in the form of continuity equation $\partial \phi(x, t) / \partial t = -\partial J / \partial x$, where J can be identified as a current which is given by

$$-J = \frac{1}{\gamma} \tilde{V}'(x)p + \frac{D}{\gamma} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \quad (23)$$

$$\tilde{V}(x) = V(x) + \sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{1}{n!} V_n(x) \overline{\langle \delta \hat{X}^n \rangle} \quad (24)$$

$D = \gamma D_{q_0}$. We now consider a cubic potential of the form, $V(x) = -(A/3)x^3 + Bx^2$ (A and B are positive constants), with a metastable minimum at $x = 0$ which is separated from the true minimum by a finite potential barrier at $x = x_b$. Linearizing the potential $V(x)$ at the barrier top we calculate the stationary flux $J(\partial \phi / \partial t = 0)$ around this point in the usual way,

$$J = \frac{\omega_b \sqrt{D}}{\sqrt{2\pi\gamma}} p(0) \exp(-E/D) \exp \left[\frac{-(1/2)V'''(x_b) \overline{\langle \delta \hat{X}^2 \rangle}_{x_b}}{D} \right] \quad (25)$$

where ω_b refers to the frequency at the barrier top and E is the activation energy ($E = V(x_b)$). Again considering an equilibrium distribution or zero current situation ($J = 0$) around $x = 0$, we linearize the potential $V(x)$ and derive from eq. (23), the population in the well as given by

$$n_a = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi D}}{\omega_0} p(0) \quad (26)$$

where ω_0 refers to the frequency in the well at $x = 0$. Based on the reasoning given earlier, we can obtain an estimate of quantum correction in (25) as $\overline{\langle \delta \hat{X}^2(t) \rangle} = (\hbar/2\omega_b) [1 + (2\omega_b/\gamma)]$ which follows from the solution of eq. (21) and a quantum average with minimum uncertainty state $\langle \delta \hat{X}^2(0) \rangle_{x=x_b} = (\hbar/2\omega_b)$. Furthermore, x_b may be expressed as $x_b = \sqrt{2E} / \omega_0$. With these simplifications the rate, k is given by the ratio J/n_a ,

$$k = \frac{\omega_0 \omega_b}{2\pi\gamma} \exp(-E/D) \exp \left[\frac{(\sqrt{2E} / \omega_0) (\hbar A / 2\omega_b) \left(1 + \frac{2\omega_b}{\gamma}\right)}{D} \right] \quad (27)$$

The expression (27) is the quantum rate of decay of a metastable state at any temperature. The quantum feature appears in two different ways. First, since D may be treated as a quantum analogue of $k_B T$ in the Boltzmann exponential factor, which reduces to $\hbar \omega_0 / 2$ in the vacuum limit and to $k_B T$ in the thermal limit, the quantum nature of the heat bath is manifested through D . Second, the quantum nature of the system is pronounced through quantum correction terms which are entangled with the nonlinearity of the

potential and vanishes in the classical limit. Thus in the classical limit, (27) reduces to the familiar expression for the Kramers'-Smoluchowski rate of escape,

$$\kappa_{cl} = \frac{\omega_0 \omega_b}{2\pi\gamma} \exp(-E/k_B T) \quad (28)$$

In the vacuum limit, i.e. at $T \rightarrow 0$, on the other hand, we have

$$\kappa_{vac} = \frac{\omega_0 \omega_b}{2\pi\gamma} \exp(-2E/\hbar\omega_0) \times \exp \left[\frac{A(\sqrt{2E}/\omega_0)(\hbar/2\omega_b) \left(1 + \frac{2\omega_b}{\gamma}\right)}{(1/2)\hbar\omega_0} \right] \quad (29)$$

The vacuum contribution corresponds to quantum tunneling at zero temperature. It is important to recall that the problem of zero temperature tunneling was first successfully addressed by Caldeira and Leggett in early eighties which subsequently initiated a major advancement in the field of macroscopic quantum tunneling. The main results in the context of overdamped limit can be summarized as follows. First, the damping causes an exponentially strong suppression of tunneling rate. Second, for strong dissipation, there is a large region where thermal and quantum fluctuation interplay so that the total rate of decay increases because the thermal activation is supplemented by quantum tunneling at finite temperature. These features can be easily recovered in the present theory. The rate coefficient in the vacuum limit κ_{vac} shows that as the temperature approaches zero tunneling decay is almost exponential. Furthermore, at finite temperature, the presence of factor $\hbar A/D\omega_b$ in the exponential in the total rate coefficient in eq. (27) implies an interplay of thermal fluctuation in D and quantum fluctuation due to $\hbar A/D\omega_b$ arising out of nonlinearity of the system. This leads to a effective reduction of the activation barrier from its classical value E resulting in an increase of the rate of decay. It is thus apparent that although the results are qualitatively comparable the underlying physical picture in the schemes (the path integral and the present one) are different and the quantum rate coefficient (27) interpolates between high temperature thermal activation and zero temperature tunneling.

Weak friction limit; quantum Kramers' equation in energy space and decay of a metastable state

To begin, we return to the generalized Langevin eq. (12).

For convenience, we will now split up the right-hand-side of eq. (16) into a time-independent and a time-dependent parts as

$$Q(t) = - \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} V^n(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(0) \rangle + g(t) \quad (30)$$

where

$$g(t) = - \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} V^n(x) [\langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(t) \rangle - \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(0) \rangle] \quad (31)$$

The Langevin eq. (12) then reduces to

$$\ddot{x} + \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) \dot{x}(\tau) + V'(x) + \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} V^n(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(0) \rangle = F(t) + g(t) \quad (32)$$

Expressing

$$V_q(x) = V(x) + \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} V^{n-1}(x) \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(0) \rangle \quad (33)$$

Eq. (32) takes the form,

$$\dot{x} = v \quad (34)$$

$$\dot{v} + \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) v(\tau) + V'_q(x) = F(t) + g(t) \quad (35)$$

Eq. (35) is our starting Langevin equation for the present section. The potential $V_q(x)$ appearing in (33) and (35) is not the classical potential but a renormalized one with quantum corrections. We now consider the following time-scales in the dynamics relevant for energy diffusion in the weak friction limit,

$$\gamma \ll 1/\tau_c \ll \omega \quad (36)$$

where γ , is the friction arising due to interaction with the bath, evaluated in the Markovian limit, τ_c the correlation time of the noise due to heat bath and ω the linearized system frequency, which for a Brownian particle is assumed to be very high. This separation of time-scales in (36) and casting of an operator Langevin equation in c -number form (34-35) allow us to implement a classical method for solving the problem of quantum energy diffusion. Following the standard procedure one can transform eqs. (34-35) to the action (J) and angle (ϕ) co-ordinates with the help of a Jacobian matrix as

$$\begin{pmatrix} J \\ \phi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \dot{x}} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial \dot{\phi}} \\ \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \phi} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{\phi} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial J} \frac{\partial x}{\partial J} \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial v} \\ \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} \end{array} - \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) v(\tau) + F(t) + g(t) \right)$$

Thus we have

$$j = \frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi} \left[- \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) v(\tau) + F(t) + g(t) \right] \quad (37)$$

$$\dot{\phi} = \omega(J) - \frac{\partial x}{\partial J} \left[- \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) v(\tau) + F(t) + g(t) \right] \quad (38)$$

Here $v(= \dot{x})$ represents the velocity of the particle. For the deterministic part of the system's Hamiltonian given by $H = (1/2)v^2 + V_q(x)$ we may write,

$$\omega(J) = \frac{dH(J)}{dJ} \quad (39)$$

Since $V_q(x)$ (see eq. (33)) contains quantum corrections, our J and ϕ are quantum (c -number) variables as implied in (33). In the absence of quantum corrections they become classical variables⁶. The canonical transformation from (x, v) space to (J, ϕ) space has been done with the deterministic Hamiltonian. We can therefore expand x and v as

$$x(J, \phi) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x_n(J) \exp(in\phi) \quad (40)$$

$$v(J, \phi) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} v_n(J) \exp(in\phi) \quad (41)$$

Inserting eqs. (40) and (41) in eqs. (37) and (38), we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} j &= -i \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} n x_n \exp(in\phi) \\ &\quad \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) v_m \exp(im\phi) \\ &\quad + iS(t) \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} n x_n \exp(in\phi) \quad (42) \\ \dot{\phi} &= \omega(J) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial x_n}{\partial J} \exp(in\phi) \\ &\quad \int_0^t d\tau \beta(t-\tau) v_m \exp(im\phi) \\ &\quad - S(t) \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial x_n}{\partial J} \exp(in\phi) \quad (43) \end{aligned}$$

where, we have expressed $S(t)$ as a sum of two terms; the noise due to heat bath, $F(t)$ and quantum correction term,

$g(t)$

$$S(t) = F(t) + g(t) \quad (44)$$

In the equations of motion (42) and (43), the argument of the damping memory kernel β is $(t - \tau)$. Now β decays to zero in a time τ_c (the correlation time). So, to deal with the integrals of eqs. (42) and (43), it is reasonable to divide the range of integration into two parts : (a) $|t - \tau| \leq \tau_c$ and (b) $t \gg \tau_c$.

With these preliminaries, one can obtain after a detailed algebra a Fokker-Planck equation for probability distribution function $P(J, \phi, t)$ which is equivalent to the eqs. (43-44) (for details see Ref. 21),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{P}(J, \phi, t)}{\partial t} &= \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial J} \left[2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 |x_n|^2 \tilde{\beta}_n^c(\omega) \left\{ \frac{\tilde{C}_n^c(\omega)}{\tilde{\beta}_n^b(\omega)} \frac{\partial}{\partial J} + \omega(J) \right\} P \right] \\ &\quad + \Gamma(J) \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \phi^2} - \Omega(J) \frac{\partial P}{\partial \phi} \quad (45) \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\Gamma(J) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{dx_n}{dJ} \right|^2 \tilde{C}_n^c(\omega) \quad (46)$$

$$\Omega(J) = \omega + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n$$

$$\left[\omega \tilde{\beta}_n^s \frac{d|x_n|^2}{dJ} - \frac{d}{dJ} \left(\tilde{C}_n^s \frac{d|x_n|^2}{dJ} \right) \right] - f_0 \mu_0 t_c \quad (47)$$

In the eqs. (45-47), $\tilde{\beta}_n^c$, $\tilde{\beta}_{n,s}^s$, \tilde{C}_n^c , \tilde{C}_n^s , f_0 and μ_0 are defined as

$$\tilde{\beta}_n^c = \int_0^{\infty} dt \beta(t) \cos(n\omega t) \quad (48)$$

$$\tilde{\beta}_n^s = \int_0^{\infty} dt \beta(t) \sin(n\omega t) \quad (49)$$

$$\tilde{C}_n^c = \int_0^{\infty} dt C(t) \cos(n\omega t) \quad (50)$$

$$\tilde{C}_n^s = \int_0^{\infty} dt C(t) \sin(n\omega t) \quad (51)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_0 &= \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \frac{\partial}{\partial J} \\ &\quad [V^n[x(t)] \{ \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(t) \rangle - \langle \delta \hat{X}^{(n-1)}(0) \rangle \}] \quad (52) \end{aligned}$$

$$\mu_0(J) = \frac{dx_0(J)}{dJ} \quad (53)$$

τ_c in eq. (47) is the 'cut-off' time upto which the quantum fluctuation remains linear in time and is approximated as $\sim 1/\omega$, as allowed by the time-scale of the problem and $C(t)$ in eqs. (50-51) represents the continuum limit of fluctuation-dissipation relation as

$$\langle F(t) F(0) \rangle_s = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty d\omega \kappa(\omega) \rho(\omega) \hbar \omega \left(\cot h \frac{\hbar \omega}{2\kappa_B T} \right) \cos \omega t \equiv C(t) \quad (54)$$

Now if the distribution function in eq. (45) is initially independent of ϕ , it satisfies the quantum diffusion equation in action space

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{P}(J, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial J} \left[\epsilon(J) \left\{ \Lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial J} + \omega(J) \right\} P \right] \quad (55)$$

where $\epsilon(J)$ and Λ are given by

$$\epsilon(J) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 |x_n|^2 \tilde{\beta}_n^c(\omega) \quad (56)$$

$$\Lambda = \Lambda(\bar{\omega}) \simeq \frac{\tilde{C}_n^c(\bar{\omega})}{\tilde{\beta}_n^c(\bar{\omega})}$$

or

$$\Lambda = \hbar \bar{\omega} [\bar{n}(\bar{\omega}) + 1/2] \quad (57)$$

Here $\bar{\omega}$ is the linearized frequency and Λ plays the typical role of $\kappa_B T$. We have

$$\omega(J) = \frac{\partial H}{\partial J} = \frac{dE}{dJ}$$

Expressing

$$\omega(J) = \nu(E) \quad (58)$$

we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial J} = \nu(E) \frac{\partial}{\partial E} \quad (59)$$

With this transformation, the quantum Kramers' equation for energy diffusion [eq. (56)] looks like,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{P}(E, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial E} \left[D(E) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial E} + \frac{1}{\Lambda} \right) \nu(E) P(E, t) \right] \quad (60)$$

where the diffusion coefficient is given by

$$D(E) = \nu(E) 2\hbar \omega \left[\bar{n}(\bar{\omega}) + \frac{1}{2} \right]$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 |x_n|^2 \int_0^\infty dt \beta(t) \cos[(n\nu(E)t)] \quad (61)$$

Eq. (61) is valid for arbitrary temperature and noise correlation. The prime quantities that determine the dynamics of for energy diffusion are the diffusion coefficients D ; the quantum analogue of $\kappa_B T$, Λ and the frequency of the dynamical system, $\nu(E)$. It is important to note that all the quantities as defined by (57), (58) and (59), respectively, contain quantum contributions. In the classical limit eq. (58) reduces to kT when $\bar{n}(\bar{\omega}) \gg 1/2$ and $\bar{n}(\bar{\omega}) (= [\exp(\hbar\bar{\omega}/k_B T) - 1]^{-1} \approx k_B T/\hbar\bar{\omega})$. Since by virtue (59) $\nu(E) = \omega(J) = \partial H/\partial J$ with H defined as $H = (1/2)\nu^2 + V_q(x)$, where $V_q(x)$ includes quantum corrections over the classical potential $V(x)$ according to eq. (33), $\nu(E)$ reduces to classical frequency in the classical limit as $\hbar \rightarrow 0$. Although the expression for the diffusion coefficient (61) looks a bit complicated and formal due to the appearance of the Fourier coefficients x_n in the summation, it is possible to read the various terms in $D(E)$ in the following way. $D(E)$ is essentially an approximate product of three terms, $\hbar\bar{\omega} [\bar{n}(\bar{\omega}) + 1/2]$, $\int_0^\infty dt \beta(t) \cos[(n\nu(E)t)]$ and $\nu(E) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 |x_n|^2$, where the n dependence of the latter two contributions have been separated out for interpretation. The integral is the Fourier transform of the memory kernel, while the sum can be shown to be equal to J (Appendix D of Ref. 6), which is the quantum action variable. In the classical limit, the quantum diffusion coefficient $D(E)$ therefore clearly reduces to the classical diffusion coefficient of Carmeli and Nitzan⁶.

Eq. (60) is the basis of calculation of energy diffusion controlled rate in the quantum domain. We start by recasting this equation in the form of a continuity equation to obtain,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{P}(E, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial j_E}{\partial E} = 0 \quad (62)$$

where j_E is the flux along the energy coordinate at time t .

The zero flux condition in (62) yields the total population, n_a , at the source well at thermal equilibrium,

$$n_a = \frac{1}{N} \frac{2\pi\Lambda}{\sqrt{\omega_0^2 + \Delta Q_0''}} \exp \left[-\frac{\Delta Q_0}{\Lambda} + \frac{(\Delta Q_0')^2}{2\Lambda(\omega_0^2 + \Delta Q_0'')} \right] \quad (63)$$

Here ω_0 is the frequency at the bottom of the source well. $\Delta Q_0, \Delta Q_0', \Delta Q_0''$ are the quantities evaluated at the bottom of the source well to have quantum contribution ΔQ to the classical energy as

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0^2 x^2 + \Delta Q_0 + \Delta Q_0' x + \frac{1}{2} \Delta Q_0'' x^2 \quad (64)$$

N in eq. (63) corresponds to the normalization constant of the distribution function.

Now with the help of flux (at the barrier top) over population method and following the procedure developed by Buttiker *et al.*²², for classical theory one can obtain the quantum non-Markovian rate of escape from a metastable well in the low-friction regime as

$$\kappa = \left[\frac{\{1 + (4\alpha A^2) / D(E_b^c)\}^{1/2} - 1}{\{1 + (4\alpha A^2) / D(E_b^c)\}^{1/2} + 1} \right] \frac{D(E_b^c)}{A^2} \frac{\sqrt{\omega_0^2 + \Delta Q_0''}}{2\pi} \times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{A} \left\{ E_b^c - \Delta Q_0 + \frac{(\Delta Q_0')^2}{2(\omega_0^2 + \Delta Q_0'')} \right\} \right] \quad (65)$$

Here α is a parameter which can be set approximately equal to one and E_b^c is the activation barrier. As noted earlier in the detailed discussion of quantum diffusion coefficient in the context of eq. (61), the diffusion coefficient $D(E)$ is contribution by the three factors and has to be evaluated at the barrier top. The main effect of the pre-exponential factor is that the rate becomes proportional to the damping coefficient and the memory kernel results in the decrease of pre-factor for increasing correlation time. The structure of the rate expression (65) suggests that it has the same form of the pre-exponential factor as that of Hanggi and Weiss²³ although its content is quantum mechanical in character. The quantum mechanical content of the rate expression lies in several quantities, e.g. quantum diffusion coefficient $D(E_b^c)$, quantum analogue of $\kappa_B T$, A as given by (60) and (57), respectively. The frequency at the bottom of the well, ω_0 as well as the classical activation energy E_b^c get modified by quantum correction $\Delta Q_0''$ and ΔQ_0 terms. The result of Hänggi and Weiss²³ for the classical non-Markovian case can then be appropriately recovered. It is thus apparent that quantum correction terms in the exponential factor is (65) depends on the nature of the potential which in turn determines the rate.

For model cubic potential of the form as employed earlier we may show that the escape rate (65) reduces to

$$\kappa = \frac{\omega_0}{2\pi} \left[\frac{\{1 + (4\alpha A^2) / \tilde{D}(J_b)\}^{1/2} - 1}{\{1 + (4\alpha A^2) / \tilde{D}(J_b)\}^{1/2} + 1} \right] \frac{\tilde{D}(J_b)}{A^2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{A} \left\{ E_b^c + \frac{A^2 \hbar^2}{4\omega_0^3} \right\} \right] \quad (66)$$

where $\tilde{D}(J_b)$ is given by

$$\tilde{D}(J_b) \simeq 2 J_b \hbar \bar{\omega}_0 \left[\bar{n}(\bar{\omega}_0) + \frac{1}{2} \right] \int_0^\infty dt \beta(t) \cos[n\omega(J_b)t] \quad (67)$$

Here J_b denotes the value of the action of the system at the barrier top and A is the nonlinear parameter of the cubic potential. It should be noted that it includes both the classical and quantum contributions. The activation energy gets modified by a contribution due to quantum correction entangled with the nonlinearity of the potential. It is important to note that the positivity of the factor $(A^2 \hbar^2) / (4\omega_0^3 A)$ in the exponential in (66) results in a larger effective activation barrier which causes a net reduction of the full rate below its corresponding classical value. This is in good agreement with the earlier observation by Griff *et al.*²⁴ and is somewhat counterintuitive – as emphasized by Hänggi *et al.*² to the fact that full rate comprises classical rate plus zero temperature tunneling. The quantum reduction of total rate in the weak friction regime is a manifestation of interplay of thermal noise and quantum fluctuation and is expected to be pronounced for systems with flat barriers, commonly encountered in absorption-desorption processes in surface phenomena².

Conclusions

Classical Kramers' equation forms the dynamical basis of Arrhenius rate law. Its quantum analogue is therefore imperative in a quantum mechanical context. Although the classical Kramers' equation is more than sixty years old and quantum Kramers' problem has been addressed in the last twenty years by various groups a quantum kramers equation which describes Brownian motion in c -number phase space in terms of a true probability distribution remained elusive. Very recently we have proposed a quantum Kramers' equation to this end and solved the problem of barrier crossing dynamics both in the high and low friction regime for arbitrary noise correlation and temperature. The present paper is a brief account of this development with an emphasis on the quantum generalization of Arrhenius rate law. The theory unifies the aspects of thermal activation and tunneling within a single description. While in the high temperature regime classical theories can be recovered both in the Markovian and non-markovian limits, the theory retains its full validity even at absolute zero where vacuum induced tunneling is the only mechanism for escape from the reactant well. The temperature-dependence of rate constant is significantly different in this regime which has a direct bearing on the exponential gas kinetics and other areas. We hope that the present formulation will be further helpful for developing a reactive flux formalism within a phase space

description to investigate the time dependence of rate constant κ in the transient regime and its approach to asymptotic value in the steady state.

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